

Impact of Price and Shopping Motive on Millennial Consumer Preferences for Offline and Online Store Formats

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ABSTRACT: Globalisation has resulted in increased competition among businesses, leading to the development of various business formats and impacting consumer behaviour. The COVID-19 pandemic has further accelerated the shift towards online businesses, prompting the emergence of different online store formats. In light of these changes, a study was conducted to investigate the impact of price and shopping motives on consumer preferences for online store formats versus physical stores. The research methodology involved distributing surveys directly to gather opinions from respondents in Surabaya, with a focus on millennial consumers. From 144 samples of this study, price and shopping motives did not significantly influence millennial consumers' preference for store formats. However, the results of the research indicate a clear preference for online shopping over physical stores among millennial consumers. This study sheds light on consumer preferences in the current market and emphasizes the growing influence of online businesses.

KEYWORDS: Store Format; Price; Shopping Motives; Millennials

INTRODUCTION

Competition in the business world takes many forms, including between modern and traditional businesses, peer modern businesses, traditional businesses and suppliers, and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. Globalization has influenced consumer preferences, leading to fierce competition among businesses to secure market share and creating various business models and changes in consumer behavior. Consumers now prioritize convenience and the ability to find a range of products in one place. The Covid-19 pandemic has hastened the trend towards online businesses over traditional brick-and-mortar ones. Factors that affect consumers' purchasing decisions include cultural norms, demographics, social status, reference groups, familial influence, and marketing activities, as well as internal factors such as perception, learning, memory, motivation, personality, emotions, and attitudes.

When businesses choose specific product characteristics, it assists consumers in determining the most suitable store for their shopping requirements. Simamora (2003, in Windya et al., 2013) defines product attributes as the elements that customers take into consideration when purchasing a product, including price, quality, features, design, after-sales service, and more. Store format refers to the combination of factors that businesses use to design their strategies, such as price, transaction convenience, and overall shopping experience (Messinger and Narasimhan, 1997, in Tripathi et al., 2008). Recently, various types of store formats have emerged, including both offline and online options. Online stores, also known as online shopping, enable buyers to browse through products and services available on the internet. According to Botha and Geldenhuys (2008), offline stores are those that involve face-to-face transactions without the use of the Internet to sell goods and services.

Assael (1998) suggests that once businesses have identified their target audience and chosen the appropriate positioning strategy, they can focus on individual stores by developing a marketing mix that appeals to the correct target segment. The price is the total value exchanged by consumers to benefit from owning and using products or services in the marketing mix (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012). Prices have a direct and significant impact on consumers and serve as a means of communication. Therefore, pricing is a crucial factor in devising strategies for different product categories. Consumer shopping motives are critical psychological factors that require attention as they can ultimately drive purchasing and consumption behaviour. Sudaryana (2011) suggests that shopping motives serve as a source of motivation, while Subagio (2011) states that they originate from specific needs that urge individuals to satisfy them over time. Thus, the persistence or encouragement of these needs motivates shopping. Shopping and consumption motives can be divided into two categories: utilitarian motives, based on the practical usefulness of shopping, and hedonic motives, driven by emotions, comfort, joy, and pleasure. Understanding these two types is critical to analyzing consumer behavior and marketing strategies.

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Researcher recognises the significant impact that store format decisions made by business professionals could have on the post-pandemic commercial environment. To investigate this further, a study titled 'The Effect of Price and Shopping Motives on Preferences for Store Format Choices among Millennial Consumers in Surabaya (Online vs Offline Store)' was conducted. The study has implications for both business owners and consumers. Business owners can use the results to select appropriate store formats, while buyers and consumers can refer to the findings when making decisions about prices and products. This study aims to investigate the impact of price and utilitarian motives on the store format preferences of Millennial consumers in Surabaya and determine the most in-demand store format among millennials in Surabaya's culinary MSME industry. This study can assist MSME players in improving their businesses' turnover by providing insights from the researcher's preparations and findings.

Price

Determining the appropriate price for products can be a difficult task, which is why it is important to set a price that accurately reflects the product's value. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012:678), the price represents the value that a consumer gives up to acquire or use a product or service. In competitive markets, price is an important tool that economic actors use to attract consumers. Price refers to the monetary amount required to acquire a set of goods and services, as noted by Swastha and Irawan (2000, as cited in Muslim, 2011). Price performs two functions in the consumer decision-making process: the allocative function, which allows consumers to achieve the highest possible satisfaction based on their purchasing preferences, and the informational function, which educates consumers about the product's components. Among the retail marketing mix components, pricing is a crucial and challenging aspect for businesses to consider, as it can directly impact their profits.

The cost of a product plays two important roles in the decision-making process of consumers. The first role involves the allocation of price, which helps consumers determine how to attain maximum benefits based on their preferences. The second role is the information role, where the price educates consumers about various product factors. The price of a product can significantly influence a consumer's decision-making process by fulfilling both roles. Pricing is a critical and challenging component of the retail marketing mix and a profit-driving element for business owners. Business owners have access to three pricing methods: break-even pricing, demand-oriented pricing, and competition-oriented pricing, and the selection of a pricing method depends on various factors (Utami,2010:240). Pricing significantly influences consumer shopping decisions, according to Tan (2011), and everyday low prices, which refer to low prices even when items are not on sale, exert a significant impact on consumers and their preferred store format, as per Moore et al. (2010, in Mettan, 2017).

Hypothesis 1 suggests that the price of products has an impact on the store format preferences of Millennial consumers in Surabaya.

According to Tan (2011), the price of a product plays a crucial role in consumer purchasing decisions. Consistently low prices, also known as everyday low prices, significantly affect the choice of retail format, according to Moore et al. (2010, cited in Mettan 2017). This impact can even extend to the retail format itself, with respondents often avoiding formats that prioritize everyday low prices. Those who prioritize low prices tend to view sales formats that rely on strategic positioning to provide everyday low prices in a negative light.

Utilitarian Motives

Consumers are driven by utilitarian motives when they believe that purchasing a product will provide them with the specific benefits they desire. This type of motivation is based on rational and objective thinking, where consumers shop for products that they genuinely need. Consumers seek to derive benefits from the products they purchase, such as economical prices, quality products, and reliable services, while maximizing their time and energy efficiency. The motive for shopping is determined by consumers' desire to fulfill their specific needs, and they often look at products to be purchased or browse various types of goods offered to avoid buying unnecessary items.

Utilitarian shopping motivation is a type of consumer behavior where shoppers tend to make purchases based on objective and rational thinking (Utami,2010:47). This behavior disregards the shopper's overall shopping experience and is solely focused on the perceived benefits of the product. Meeting these utilitarian motives can lead to shopper loyalty towards stores that offer products tailored to such needs. A study conducted in India by Cherukiri (2010, in Mettan, 2017) found that consumers generally prefer retail stores that sell the products they need or are looking for.

Hypothesis 2 suggests that the utilitarian motive has an impact on the store format preferences of millennial consumers in Surabaya.

Subagio (2011) found that retail stores that cater to customers' utilitarian needs tend to inspire loyalty. This is corroborated by Cherukiri's study conducted in India (2010, in Mettan, 2017), which suggests that customers choose stores based on product availability. Baker et al. (1994) note that the quality and convenience of products and services offered in a store significantly impact customers' evaluations of it. This leads to an increase in utilitarian consumption. Subagio (2011) highlights that customers' needs

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drive utilitarian consumption motives. Retailers or MSME players that fulfill these needs are more likely to achieve customer satisfaction. Providing a positive shopping experience while fulfilling customers' needs may motivate them to revisit the store.

Hedonic Motives

Hedonic shopping motivation, as defined by Subagio (2010), pertains to an individual's desire for a shopping environment that evokes happiness and pleasure. This desire generates arousal, which is the level of alertness, excitement, or stimulation that a person experiences. Consumers who feel positive emotions while shopping are likely to exhibit this hedonic behavior. These individuals enjoy shopping and find it captivating. Since hedonic motivation is influenced by subjective or emotional reasoning, it includes aesthetic factors, desires, sensual pleasures, and emotional responses. Utami (2010:47) argues that this impulse prompts shoppers to purchase items because shopping itself is enjoyable, irrespective of the benefits of the products. According to Babin et al. (1994), as cited in Utami (2010:47), the emotional aspect of buying pertains to the buyer's emotions. As a result, customers may experience emotions such as happiness, dislike, or anger while shopping, or view shopping as an adventure. Hedonic impulses have a more substantial impact on buying decisions than utilitarian motivation since utilitarian benefits are primarily objective features of products, while hedonic benefits consist of emotional responses, sensory pleasures, and aspirations.

The hedonic theory argues that buyers' primary objective is to seek pleasurable experiences while avoiding negative ones. Hedonic consumption meets subjective and experiential needs, such as excitement, confidence, and emotional responses. According to Solomon (2002:105), cited in Utami (2010:49), customers typically depend on products to fulfill such needs. Hedonic consumption evokes substantial responses, including multisensory engagement, fantasy, delusion, and emotional aspects. Subagio (2011) suggests that fulfilling hedonic motives can enhance customer loyalty to stores that offer customized promotions based on impulsive hedonic motives. Furthermore, shopping for hedonic motives is emotionally driven, inducing comfort, joy, and pleasure.

Hypothesis 3 suggests that the hedonic motive has an impact on the store format preferences of millennial consumers in Surabaya.

Subagio (2011) suggests that emotions such as comfort, joy, and pleasure drive hedonic purchasing behavior. Thus, MSME actors or sellers must provide satisfactory experiences to retain a happy and content customer base. Positive shopping experiences correlate directly with future patronage as consumers return to the same establishment. Objective satisfaction is a key factor in shaping their future shopping preferences.

Offline and Online Stores

In recent times, an increasing number of customers prefer to shop through both online and offline channels. Some experts suggest that combining these channels can create a "perfect synergy" (Beck, 2013), and businesses believe that by integrating online and offline channels, they can leverage the advantages of each. It is not possible to isolate online and offline sales channels, as online sales are conducted via the internet, while offline sales occur in physical stores.

Online distribution channels do not serve as substitutes for offline distribution channels; rather, they complement each other. Concurrently, the current popular offline distribution channels will continue to flourish with an increase in online purchases (Agarwal, 2012, cited in Wang & Goldfarb, 2016). However, considerable research has centered on the competition between online and offline retailers, emphasizing that they serve as substitutes and highlighting the significance of local demographics, product type, and proximity to physical stores in determining the degree of consumer substitutability. The literature also emphasizes the need to focus on competitors in this field.

Figure 1. Research Model
Source: Primary Data, Processed (2021)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research study uses a causal approach to examine the relationship between two variables and how one variable affects the other. To find out how price, utilitarian motivation, and hedonic motivation affect the store format preference of Millennial consumers in Surabaya, a survey method is employed by asking respondents a series of questions.

Variable Identification

The variables used consist of Dependent variables and Independent variables. The variables in question are:

- a. Independent Variable (X):
 - Price (X1)
 - Utilitarian Motives (X2)
 - Hedonic Motives (X3)
- b. Dependent Variable:
 - Store format (Y)
 - Online Store = 1
 - Offline Stores = 2

Operational Definition of Variables

Price

Price refers to consumer considerations about how much they will pay for goods and services compared to what they will get (Zeithaml, 1988, in Kusdiyah, 2012). The price must be able to show the value and standard of the product to be consumed. Price indicators consist of three components: low prices, discounted prices, and prices that match the quality (Carpenter et al., 2010; Muslim, 2011).

Utilitarian Motives

Purchasing an item with the intention of benefiting from it is referred to as the utilitarian motive. The primary objective of consumer shopping is to fulfill their requirements. Cardoso and Pinto (2010) conducted research on this variable and identified the following indicators: Finding the desired items, Access to stores with complete inventory, Consumers who plan their shopping and Consumers who shop to satisfy their needs.

Hedonic Motives

Hedonic consumption is the consumption of goods and services by individuals for reasons of pleasure and happiness. The indicators for this variable were developed according to Cardoso and Pinto's research (2010). Consumers search for discounted products while shopping, as well as to explore the availability of new items and to alleviate stress.

Store Format

According to Botha, Bothma, and Geldenhuys (2008), there are two distinct types of stores: offline and online. The former refers to the purchase of goods and services directly from a physical store, while the latter refers to purchases made through the Internet

Data Type and Source

Quantitative methods will be used in this study, based on the numerical data obtained from the respondents' scored answers. The primary data sources for this study will be the individuals identified by the source.

Variable Measurement

In order to measure a specific attribute, the research should use an interval scale which provides equal intervals between objects. For instance, a study on how Millennial Consumers in Surabaya choose a store format based on Price, Utilitarian Motives, and Hedonic Motives, uses a Likert scale to measure variables. Participants are asked to express their preference by choosing a category rating system that ranges from "strongly agree" (Score 5) to "strongly disagree" (Score 1). The value of each item is assessed by comparing it with the overall score.

Data Collection Tools and Methods

The research technique utilized in this study involved asking ten questions to Surabaya's Millennial shoppers who have made purchases both online and offline. The data was gathered through a survey method.

Population and Sample

The study focused on millennial consumers who engaged in both online and offline shopping in Surabaya. The researchers used a purposive sampling method to select a total of 150 participants who met specific inclusion criteria, such as being between the ages of 20 and 40 and having a history of shopping online and in-person. It is worth noting that the sample size was only a subset of a larger population with similar characteristics. To ensure a reasonable sample error, the researchers tripled the recommended sample size of five times the number of indicator variables, as suggested by Hair et al. (2015).

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Data Analysis Technique

The research methodology used in this study involves the use of logistic analysis, which is a statistical technique that uses multiple variables to predict the probability of an event occurring in the dependent variable.

Validity Test

To ensure accurate measurement, a measuring scale must measure what it's intended to measure. Researchers can evaluate an instrument's validity by setting a significance level of either 5% or 0.05. An instrument is deemed valid if it exceeds the set threshold.

Reliability Test

Ensuring the reliability of a measurement scale score is essential for any research study because it indicates the consistency and stability of the results. According to Ghozali (2013), a research instrument is considered reliable if the value of Cronbach Alpha is greater than 0.60. Hence, reliable research instruments are critical for obtaining precise and dependable outcomes.

Equation Model

$$\text{LnY} = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4$$

Description:

- Constant Value (b_0)
- Price Value (b_1)
- Utilitarian Motives Value (b_2)
- Hedonic Motives Value (b_3)
- Price (X_1)
- Utilitarian Motives (X_2)
- Hedonic Motives (X_3)
- Store format (Y)
 - Online Store = 1
 - Offline Stores = 2

Classification Accuracy Test

Logistic regression is a method of categorizing people into either "success" or "failure" groups based on specific factors, much like discriminant analysis. One way to measure the accuracy of the model is to use the hit ratio, where a value of more than 50% usually indicates a reliable logistic regression. Additionally, Hair et al. (2010, p. 431) offer additional advice on modeling logistic regression.

Model Fit Test

Logistic regression analysis is a statistical technique that evaluates how well the collected data fits the regression model. This evaluation process involves two tests: Nagelkerke and Hosmer-Lemeshow. The Nagelkerke test calculates the R^2 coefficient, which is the proportion of variation in the Y variable that is explained by the X variable. Whenever technical terms are used, they will be explained. On the other hand, the Hosmer-Lemeshow test examines two hypotheses: H_0 and H_1 . H_0 assumes that the model fits the data well, while H_1 assumes the contrary. The probability level is used to decide which hypothesis is accepted. If the probability level is greater than the specified α level, H_0 is accepted. In contrast, if the probability level is less than α , then the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted (Hair et al. 2010: 431).

Hypothesis Test

Logistic regression analysis is a statistical technique that evaluates the accuracy and reliability of hypotheses. The validity of hypotheses is confirmed if their probability is less than the specified α level. According to the author, a hypothesis is considered acceptable if the probability level is $\alpha \leq 0.05$. The Sig table in the Variables in Equation table can be used to determine the acceptance of hypotheses. (Hair et al. 2010: 432).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The surveys were handed out over a period of one month, starting from January 2021 and ending in the same year.

Table 1. Research Sample Selection

Description	Number of Respondents
Total Questionnaires distributed	Shared via Google Form
Total questionnaires returned	203

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Total Questionnaires Completed	144
Sample Size (n)	144

Source: Processed by Researchers (2021)

Validity Test

According to the information presented in Table 2, it can be concluded that the questionnaire items are suitable and valid for use as the significance value is below 0.05.

Table 2. Old Validity Test

Indicator	Pearson Correlation Value	Value - p	Conclusion
<i>Price</i>			
X11	0,755	0,000	Valid
X12	0,842	0,000	Valid
X13	0,710	0,000	Valid
<i>Utilitarian Motives</i>			
X21	0,689	0,000	Valid
X22	0,780	0,000	Valid
X23	0,716	0,000	Valid
X24	0,791	0,000	Valid
<i>Hedonic Motives</i>			
X31	0,442	0,000	Valid
X32	0,870	0,000	Valid
X33	0,857	0,000	Valid

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

In Table 3, one of the indicators in the hedonic motives variable was removed due to insufficient reliability. After analyzing the data with IBM Statistics 26, it was found that deleting indicator X3.1 from the hedonic motives variable would improve its reliability.

Table 3. New Validity Test

Indicator	Pearson Correlation Value	Value - p	Conclusion
<i>Price</i>			
X11	0,755	0,000	Valid
X12	0,842	0,000	Valid
X13	0,710	0,000	Valid
<i>Utilitarian Motives</i>			
X21	0,689	0,000	Valid
X22	0,780	0,000	Valid
X23	0,716	0,000	Valid
X24	0,791	0,000	Valid
<i>Hedonic Motives</i>			
X32	0,905	0,000	Valid
X33	0,935	0,000	Valid

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

Reliability Test

A questionnaire is considered reliable if the Cronbach alpha coefficient ≥ 0.6 , then the indicator can be reliable (Ghozali, 2006: 42).

Table 4. Reliability Test of Duration

Indicator	Value - Cronbach Alpha Coefficient	Value - Cronbach Alpha	Summary
Price (X1)	0.6	0,653	Reliable
Utilitarian Motives (X2)	0.6	0,722	Reliable

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<i>Hedonic Motives (X3)</i>	0.6	0,589	Unreliable
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Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

Table 4 shows that IBM Statistics 26 has determined that the Reliability of the hedonic motives variable is insufficient. One indicator in the hedonic motives variable must be removed to enhance it. After examining the results, the IBM program recommends removing indicator X3.1 to improve the Reliability of hedonic motives. The outcomes can be found in Table 5 after conducting Reliability by removing X3.1.

Table 5. New Reliability Test

Indicator	Value - Cronbach Alpha Coefficient	Value Cronbach Alpha	Summary
Price (X1)	0.6	0,653	Reliable
<i>Utilitarian Motives (X2)</i>	0.6	0,722	Reliable
<i>Hedonic Motives (X3)</i>	0.6	0,813	Reliable

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

The results in Table 5 illustrate the outcome of a rerun conducted after removing indicator X3.1. Eliminating this indicator led to a considerable improvement in the reliability score of the hedonic motives variable, X3, relative to the prior findings.

Classification Accuracy Test

If the cut value in regression exceeds 50%, we can consider the classification accuracy accurate. This means the logistic regression is workable, and the respondents have been correctly classified.

Table 6. Correctness of Old Classification

			Predicted		
			Y		Percentage Correct
			<i>Online</i>	<i>Offline</i>	
Step 1	Y	<i>Online</i>	79	5	94.0
		<i>Offline</i>	56	4	6.7
Overall Percentage					57.6

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

Table 6 shows 84 respondents who chose *Online Stores*, 79 respondents were classified correctly, and five people were classified incorrectly, so the percentage of respondents who were classified correctly was $79/84 = 94.0\%$. As for respondents who chose *Offline* out of 60 respondents, four were classified correctly, and the remaining 56 were classified incorrectly. Therefore, the percentage of respondents classified correctly for *Offline Store* is $4/60 = 6.7\%$. It can be concluded that overall, the respondents who have been classified correctly are 57.6%; this result shows that the classification value is above the *cut* value of 50%, so the logistic Regression in this research is feasible. Meanwhile, based on the results of data reprocessing due to the deleted x3.1 indicator, the results show the following.

Table 7. New Classification Accuracy

Observed			Predicted		
			Y		Percentage Correct
			<i>Online</i>	<i>Offline</i>	
Step 1	Y	<i>Online</i>	78	6	92.9
		<i>Offline</i>	56	4	6.7
Overall Percentage					57.6

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

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The data provided in the study shows the accuracy of classifying respondents who chose Online Stores and Offline Stores. The data analysis suggests that the logistic regression used in this study is viable. The overall correct classification rate of the participants is 56.9%, meaning the classification value is above the minimum threshold of 50%. Although there is a decline in the classification value for location choice between online and offline stores, the overall percentage still exceeds 50%, proving this research's practicality.

Equation Model

$$\ln Y = 1.441 - 0.346 \text{ Price} - 0.167 \text{ Utilitarian Motives} + 0.099 \text{ Hedonic Motives}$$

As per the given equation, it is evident that consumers opt for the Online Store due to the low prices and practical reasons, as indicated by the negative position in the β number for these variables. However, regarding the hedonic motives variable, consumers prefer shopping at brick-and-mortar stores, as it shows a positive result in the β number.

Model Fit Test

The Hosmer and Lemeshow test aims to test two hypotheses - H0 and H1. H0 suggests that the model is a good fit for the data, while H1 suggests that it is not. The decision between H0 and H1 is based on the probability level, with the acceptance of H0 or H1 being determined by whether the probability level is greater or less than the α level of 0.1. If the probability level is greater than 0.1, then H0 is accepted. If the probability level is less than or equal to 0.1, H0 is rejected, and H1 is accepted. The Hosmer and Lemeshow test provides the results to help make this determination.

Table 8. Hosmer and Lemeshow Test 1

Step	Chi-Square	df	Sig
1	6.863	8	0,551

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

The information presented in Table 8 shows that the value of χ^2 is 6.863, and the corresponding p-value is 0.551. When the hypothesis was tested with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.1$, the obtained p-value of 0.551 was greater than 0.05, which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (H0). Therefore, it can be concluded that the logistic regression model is fitting the data. However, due to the unreliable variable X3, the data was re-run, and the new results are as follows:

Table 9. Hosmer and Lemeshow Test #2

Step	Chi-Square	df	Sig
1	6.296	8	0.614

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

Table 9 displays that the value of χ^2 is 6.296 with a p-value of 0.614. The hypothesis is tested with an alpha of 0.1, and the p-value of 0.614 is greater than 0.05, which leads to the acceptance of H0. Therefore, it can be concluded that the logistic regression model is an appropriate fit for the data. The Nagelkerke Model Summary Table provides a summary of R², indicating that the variability of the constant Y can be explained by variable X. The Model Summary outcomes are given below.

Table 10. Model Summary #1

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox and Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R square
1	193.979 ^a	0,011	0,015

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

According to the information presented in Table 10, the Nagelkerke R square value is 0.015, indicating that just 1.5% of the changes in Y can be attributed to the three X variables, while the majority of the changes (98.5%) are caused by other variables. As a result, the data was reanalyzed due to the untrustworthy nature of X3.

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Table 11. Model Summary #2

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox and Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R square
1	193.570 ^a	0,014	0,019

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

According to the data presented in Table 11, the three X variables have a Nagelkerke R squared value of 0.019. This means that they can only explain 1.9% of the variation in Y, while the remaining 98.1% is caused by other factors. It was observed that by removing indicators in variable X3 or hedonic motives, the resulting R squared increased from 1.5% to 1.9%.

Hypothesis Test

When testing a hypothesis, one can use the p-value to make a determination. If the p-value is lower than the predetermined α level of 0.05, then the hypothesis can be considered valid. However, if the p-value is higher than the α level of 0.05, then the hypothesis must be disregarded.

Table 12. Summary of Hypothesis Test Results #1

Hypothesis	B	Wald	Sig.	Summary
H1 : Price-->Shop Format	-0,367	1.386	0,239	H1 Rejected
H2 : <i>Utilitarian</i> Motives-->Shop Format	-0,147	0.249	0,617	H2 Rejected
H3 : <i>Hedonic Motives</i> --> Store Format	0,014	0.005	0,945	H3 Rejected
Constant	1.663	0.830	0,362	

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

The researchers have summarized the hypotheses tested in Table 12. The findings suggest that these three hypotheses have no statistical significance and do not affect the decision of millennial consumers in choosing a store format, whether online or offline. Due to the unreliable X3 variable, the researchers had to rerun the data, which led to the creation of Table 13.

Table 13. Summary of Hypothesis Test Results #2

Hypothesis	B	Wald	Sig.	Summary
H1 : Price-->Shop Format	-0,346	1.213	0,271	H1 Rejected
H2 : <i>Utilitarian</i> Motives-->Shop Format	-0,167	0.328	0,567	H2 Rejected
H3 : <i>Hedonic Motives</i> --> Store Format	0,099	0.413	0,520	H3 Rejected
Constant	1.441	0.637	0,425	

Source: Appendix, processed by researchers (2021)

According to the findings presented in Table 13, after examining three different hypotheses, researchers have concluded that there is no significant impact on the preference of millennial consumers towards online or offline stores in terms of store format.

CONCLUSION

The study's model effectively measures the factors influencing consumers' choice of store format, including price variables, utilitarian motives, and hedonic motives, according to the results of the model fit test. The logistic regression analysis conducted by researchers led to the following conclusion:

Hypothesis 1 cannot prove that price significantly affects millennial consumers' choice of store format. Based on the price variable, consumers tend to prefer online stores over offline stores.

While it cannot be proven that utilitarian motives significantly influence millennial consumers' store format preferences, this variable suggests that consumers are more likely to favor online stores over brick-and-mortar stores.

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It is unclear whether hedonic motives significantly impact millennial consumers' store format selection. However, the analysis excluded hedonic motives, which are a common reason why consumers prefer shopping at physical stores rather than online. It is important to note that this is a subjective evaluation and should be clearly marked as such.

REFERENCES

- 1) Assael, Henry. (1998). *Marketing*, New York: Harcourt Brace and Company New York.
- 2) Beck, J. (2013). Multichannel Marketing Is a Perfect Storm of Synergies. *blog entry, Gartner (July 3)*, <http://blogs.gartner.com/jennifer-beck/multichannel-marketing-is-a-perfect-storm-of-synergies-2>.
- 3) Botha, J.; Bothma, C.; Geldenhuys, P. (2008). *Managing E-commerce in Business*. Cape Town: Juta and Company Ltd. p. 3. ISBN 9780702173042.
- 4) Cardoso, [Ribeiro P.](#) and [Carvalho Pinto, S.](#) (2010), "Hedonic and utilitarian shopping motivations among Portuguese young adult consumers", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 38 No. 7, pp. 538-558. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09590551011052124>
- 5) Carpenter, J. M., and Moore, M. (2010). Product Attributes and Retail Format Choice Among U.S. Apparel Purchases, *Journal of Textile and Apparel, Technology and Management*, Vol. 6, Issue 4.
- 6) Durianto, Sugiarto, dan Sijinjak, Tony (2001). *Strategi Menaklukkan Pasar Melalui Riset Ekuitas dan Perilaku Merek*, Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 7) Ghozali, Imam. (2013). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 21*.
- 8) Hair, J. F., Wolfinbarger, M., Money, A. H., Samouel, P., & Page, M. J. (2015). *Essentials of business research methods*. Routledge.
- 9) Hair, Joseph F., JR., Anderson, Rolp E., Black, W. C., and Babin, B. J., 2010, *Multivariate Data Analysis: A Global Perspective*, 7th ed., USA: Prentice Hall International, Inc.
- 10) Kotler.P, and Armstrong, Gary. (2012). *Principles of Marketing*, 14th ed., England: Pearson Education Limited.
- 11) Kusdiyah, Ike. (2012), Persepsi Harga, Persepsi Merek, Persepsi Nilai, Dan Keinginan Pembelian Ulang Jasa Clinic Kesehatan (Studi Kasus Erha Clinic Surabaya), *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, Vol. 7, No. 1, April 2012, STIE Asia, Malang, pp 25-32.
- 12) Mettan. S. V. (2017)., Pengaruh harga, private brand, utilitarian motives, dan hedonic motives terhadap pilihan format ritel di Surabaya (Uji preferensi antara Indomaret dan Giant Hypermarket)
- 13) Muslim, M. I. (2011). Analisis Pengaruh Merchandise, Promosi, Atmosfer dalam Gerai, Pelayanan Ritel, dan Harga terhadap Keputusan Pembelian, Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- 14) Subagio, Hartono. (2011) Pengaruh Atribut Supermarket terhadap Motif Belanja Hedonik Motif Utilitarian dan Loyalitas Konsumen, *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, Vol. 6 No.1, April 2011:pp 8-21.
- 15) Sudaryana, Arif. (2011). Perilaku Konsumen dalam Berbelanja pada Supermarket di Yogyakarta, *Jurnal Akmenika UPY* Vol 8: pp 67-83.
- 16) Tan, E. R. (2011). Pengaruh Faktor, Harga, Promosi, dan Pelayanan terhadap Keputusan Konsumen untuk Belanja di Alfamart Surabaya, *Jurnal Kewirausahaan*, Vol. 5 No. 2, Desember 2011, pp 25-30.
- 17) Tripathi, S., and Sinha, P. K.. (2008), *Choice of a Retail Stores and Retail Store Format a Hierarchical Logit Model*, *Journal of Management AHMEDABAD*, India.
- 18) Utami, C. W. (2010). *Manajemen Ritel: Strategi dan Implementasi Operasional Bisnis Ritel Modern di Indonesia*, Edisi Kedua, Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 19) Wang, K., & Goldfarb, A. (2016). Can offline stores drive online sales?. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 54(5), 706-719.
- 20) Windya Eka Arifiana, Srihandi Kumadji, dan Dahlan Fanani. (2013). Pengaruh Atribut Produk Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Survei Pada Ibu Rumah Tangga Perumahan Bumi Asri Sengkaling Rw 05 Desa Mulyoagung Kecamatan Dau Kabupaten Malang Pembeli Deterjen Rinso).